

Research Paper

Experimental study on the influence of electrical conductivity of hygroscopic compounds on the performance of a hygroscopic cycle

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ABSTRACT

Dry climate conditions and the risk of desertification have increased significantly due to the effects of climate change. This fact, combined with the growing energy demand, leads to the need of research focused on improving the performance and efficiency of power plants. In the Hygroscopic Cycle Technology, recently implemented at industrial scale, steam condensation is performed in an absorber using solutions of hygroscopic compounds in water. Hygroscopic effects increase the condensing temperature for a given pressure, allowing the implementation of dry coolers at high ambient temperatures and eliminating cooling water consumption. In this work, due to their relevance in the cycle performance and control, the influence of the concentration of hygroscopic salts in the cycle has been studied, providing insight into proper operational ranges and key parameters. An experimental study of the influence of make-up water quality, with the concentration of impurities measured by water electrical conductivity and cycle mass flow ratio values has been performed in a pilot plant. The results, used to validate a mass and species conservation model, have allowed to obtain operational charts of the cycle and may help to reduce the amount of instrumentation required for cycle control. It was found that the decrease in electrical conductivities with boiler blowdowns in the cycle stabilized at a boiler blowdown ratio of 5%. Blowdown ratios above 10% did not result in substantially lower boiler Cycles Of Concentration in comparison with the increase of thermal energy losses and pumping power (0.42 kJ/kg for each additional 1% of blowdown). It was also found that the ratio between the cooling reflux and turbine steam conductivity had to be higher than 1.1 for condensation by absorption to occur, and that a minimum blowdown ratio of 0.04% was required to avoid using a droplet separator to control live steam quality. Hence, a compromise in the boiler blowdown ratio must be found for each particular application. Finally, hygroscopic effects in condensing pressure and temperature have been experimentally verified at pilot plant scale, leading to potentially higher cycle power output values and higher temperatures in the cooling stream of industrial power cycles, which may make it easier to reject heat from the cycle.

1. Introduction

In 2021, over 82.3% of global primary energy came from fossil fuels such as coal, gas and oil [1]. Moreover, total energy production has increased by 20,000 TWh (17.3%) in the last 10 years [2]. In this context, the decarbonization and energy transition towards renewable sources are of vital importance to fulfill the objectives of the Paris Agreement [3]. Additionally, the United Nations World Water Development Report [4] states that, by 2030, the planet will face a 40% water deficit. Currently, worldwide power generation accounts for around

10% of global water consumption, mainly used as cooling water [5]. Therefore, bold improvements in several areas must be performed, such as improving energy efficiency and achieving low-carbon power plants, industries, buildings and transport systems [6].

Combined and steam cycles are the most widely used technologies for power generation, being the Rankine Cycle (RC), powered by steam, the most prevalent in thermal power plants [7]. Alternatives to this cycle are Organic Rankine Cycles (ORCs), which operate with organic fluids [8] to extract heat from low-grade thermal sources, or Goswami and Kalina cycles [9]. Nevertheless, high ambient temperatures considerably reduce the cooling capacity of refrigeration processes, turning global

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Nomenclature			
c	concentration of impurities	D	bleeding to deaerator
k	electrical conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)	F	feedwater stream
\dot{m}	mass flowrate (kg/s)	H_2O	pure water
P	pressure	M	make-up stream
T	temperature	R	cooling reflux stream
\dot{V}	volume flowrate (L/h)	S	steam stream
<i>Greek symbol</i>		<i>Abbreviation</i>	
ϕ	flow ratio	COC	Cycles of Concentration
Δ	increment	HCT	Hygroscopic Cycle Technology
<i>Subscript</i>		ORC	Organic Rankine Cycle
B	blowdown stream	PLC	Programmable Logic Controller
C	condensate stream	RC	Rankine Cycle
Cond	condensing	SCADA	Supervisoy Control And Data Acquisition
		SWAS	Steam and Water Analysis System
		TDS	Total Dissolved Solids

warming into a challenge for the erection of thermal power plants [10,11]. In addition, a continuous and guaranteed water source in the surroundings of power plants is a vital requirement to feed open refrigeration systems [12].

In this context, the Hygroscopic Cycle Technology (HCT) may represent an interesting alternative. The cycle works with a solution of hygroscopic compounds and water coming from boiler blowdowns that allows steam condensation inside an absorber, replacing the traditional condenser. The ebullioscopic effect increases the condensing temperature for a given pressure, allowing the use of dry coolers for heat dissipation to higher ambient temperatures while avoiding water consumption [12]. A pilot plant [13] was developed to study the influence of the concentration of hygroscopic compounds on the cycle performance. The results showed that the increase in saline concentration significantly raised HCT cooling temperatures, with values over 15°C compared to RC for the same condensing pressure. Dry coolers may be implemented, significantly reducing their power consumption, and avoiding using cooling water. This led to a net electrical power output increase of up to 17.4% with respect to RC for a cooling stream temperature of 30°C . In addition, if the condensing temperature is kept constant, the condensing pressure is reduced, increasing the enthalpy jump across the turbine and thus the cycle net electrical efficiency up to 5.3% with respect to a traditional Rankine cycle.

In contrast to other cycles specifically designed for low-grade thermal sources, HCT may be applied to any power generation range. The advantages of HCT implementation were verified in an existing 12.5 MW biomass power plant in Palenciana (Córdoba, Spain), becoming the first reference of HCT at an industrial scale [14]. The net electrical efficiency of the plant, as well as the cooling capacity, were improved, working even at ambient temperatures over 45°C . The existing cooling tower was removed, resulting in a substantial reduction of water consumption with annual savings of $229,200\text{ m}^3$ raw water. In addition, the average energy supplied to the grid increased by 75 MWh/month, with an average annual increase in net electrical efficiency of 2.5%.

The working fluid plays a key role in the performance and operation of steam cycles, with strict requirements regarding material protection, service life, and overall working conditions [15]. Water impurities corrode the equipment and may also precipitate in the evaporator in the form of scaling, so boiler purges are required [16]. Boilers are generally equipped with automatic purge water systems at the bottom and surface levels [17]. The bottom purge removes accumulated solids and sludge when required through a cut-off valve [18], whereas the surface purge uses an actuated valve with a conductivity sensor to keep the

concentration of impurities within the operating range [19]. HCT boilers only need the surface-level purge since no precipitation of solids or sludge is expected [13].

The water losses from the cycle are restored by make-up water previously treated to match the cycle target values [20]. Water treatment aims to reduce the concentration of dissolved salts (mainly silica, bicarbonates and iron), as well as dissolved gasses, to keep electrical conductivity and hardness below a particular value [21,22]. Therefore, monitoring the concentration of water impurities both in the cycle water and the make-up water becomes of high importance for proper operation. In industrial environments, the standard procedure to control the concentration is monitoring water electrical conductivity values (Steam and Water Analysis System - SWAS) [23]. Rankine cycles require a water purity that corresponds to almost demineralized water, resulting in electrical conductivity values lower than $1\ \mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ [24]. On the other hand, HCT cycles may work with several water qualities, ranging from demineralized through osmotic and mains up to high concentration salt-water mixtures [13]. However, the steam flow outlet from the boiler usually drags liquid droplets to the turbine inlet that have the same composition as the boiler mixture [25]. Turbines require specific steam grades since impurities reduce their performance through blade and disc pitting, erosion, and corrosion, leading to mechanical stresses that damage the turbine [26,27]. As damage probability associated to these phenomena increases with impurity concentrations and exposure time, according to [28], live steam electrical conductivity must not exceed $0.2\ \mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ [29] to guarantee proper performance in continuous operation.

Until now, industrial HCT power plants operate with low hygroscopic compound concentrations, with successfully implemented generation facilities of up to 25 MW [30]. Nevertheless, despite their relevance, the influence of the concentration of hygroscopic salts in the cycle has not yet been studied. The main objective of this work is to gain insight into the proper operation ranges of the Hygroscopic Cycle for low concentrations of hygroscopic compounds, identifying the key control parameters. With this aim, an experimental study of the influence of make-up water quality and cycle mass flow ratio values has been performed in a HCT pilot plant. The results, coupled to a mass and species conservation model, allowed to obtain relationships between salt concentrations and mass flows throughout the cycle depending on the key control parameters. Parallely, it has been possible to verify and identify the hygroscopic effects on the thermodynamic properties of the salt-water mixture at the cycle absorption stage. The results have allowed to generate operational charts for the proper operation of the technology.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Experimental pilot plant

The experimental tests of this work were performed in an HCT pilot plant located in Gijón (Spain) [13], depicted in Fig. 1. Further details about the plant operation may be found in [13,31].

Fig. 2 shows the flow diagram of the HCT pilot plant, where a Supervisory Control And Data Acquisition (SCADA) system controls and collects all the experimental data. The pilot plant has a steam generation capacity of 110 kg/h at 14 bar and 200 °C, produced by a 100-kW pyro-tubular natural gas boiler. An expansion valve was installed at the boiler outlet to simulate steam conditions at the turbine outlet. A programmable logic controller (PLC) recorded the isenthalpic expansion at the valve, allowing to estimate the instantaneous electrical power output of the cycle turbine. After expansion, the steam is condensed in the absorber, the core component of the HCT technology. For this purpose, the cooling reflux stream from the dry coolers, containing hygroscopic compounds, condenses the steam at the absorber. These hygroscopic compounds come from the condensate and the boiler blowdown. Before recirculating the boiler blowdown, the stream passes through a closed enthalpic recuperator to preheat the boiler feedwater, which is then pumped back into the boiler. The concentration of hygroscopic compounds changes along the HCT cycle for the correct operation of the technology, so different colors have been used to identify the different stream concentrations in Fig. 2, with \dot{m}_i and k_i representing the mass flowrate and electrical conductivity.

A 2 m³ atmospheric tank (additive tank) was included in the plant to prepare saline mixtures to adjust the electrical conductivity of the make-up water when values higher than the mains water value were required [32], as shown in Fig. 3. A demineralizing module for water treatment was also integrated, allowing water qualities ranging from demineralized to osmotic with electrical conductivity values from 0.3 to 20 μS/cm [33]. The minimum conductivity of the local water supply in Gijón (Spain) is 150 μS/cm [34], so sodium chloride (NaCl) was used to adjust make-up water when conductivities above that value were necessary. Furthermore, chemical additives (amines) [35] were used to avoid scale formation and corrosion due to oxygen, other dissolved gases, and chlorides [36].

Boiler blowdowns are continuously performed in the HCT cycle to provide hygroscopic compounds for steam absorption to occur. This

requires a more thorough knowledge and monitoring of the concentration evolution inside the boiler. With this purpose, Cycles Of Concentration (COC) become a key factor for boiler control, being defined as the ratio between Total Dissolved Solids (TDS) in the boiler water and the boiler feedwater [16,37]. COC may be obtained by dividing the concentration of impurities in the boiler water and the boiler feedwater, as in Eq. (1):

$$COC = \frac{c_B}{c_F} \quad (1)$$

where c_B is the concentration of impurities in the boiler water, which is the same as in boiler blowdown, and c_F the concentration in the boiler feedwater. A progressive increase of COC implies the reduction of fuel consumption, chemical addition, make-up water and purge flowrates. Nevertheless, this increase entails greater probabilities of incrustations and steam contamination, damaging the boiler and the turbine [38,39]. Hence, COC must be optimized by a trade-off between cycle efficiency and equipment durability. However, the thermal and chemical recovery of purges in the HCT enthalpic recuperator allows to reduce COC, obtaining purer steam without consuming additional resources.

With the increase in ion concentrations, the electrical conductivity increases as well; in most cases, following a proportional relationship [40]. As current industrial HCT facilities use low hygroscopic compound concentration values, the study has been focused on the concentration range below 10%. For low concentration values, it has been experimentally observed that electrical conductivity of solutions has a linear dependence on concentration [41,42,43]; therefore, for the concentration ranges studied in this work, Eq. (1) turns into:

$$COC = \frac{c_B}{c_F} \approx \frac{k_B}{k_F} \quad (2)$$

where k_B is the electrical conductivity of the boiler blowdown (μS/cm) and k_F is the electrical conductivity of the boiler feedwater (μS/cm). A dimensionless variable, called boiler blowdown flow ratio ϕ_B , may be defined as the ratio between the mass flowrate of boiler blowdowns \dot{m}_B and feedwater \dot{m}_F :

$$\phi_B = \frac{\dot{m}_B}{\dot{m}_F} \quad (3)$$

The control of this parameter is vital for the proper operation of HCT. When ϕ_B is too low, the concentration of hygroscopic compounds in the

Fig. 1. General view - HCT pilot plant.

Fig. 2. Flow diagram - HCT pilot plant.

Fig. 3. Additive tank, demineralizing module and natural gas boiler – HCT pilot plant.

boiler becomes too high and may damage the turbine; in addition, it is possible that not enough hygroscopic compounds reach the absorber, preventing the HCT from working. On the other hand, very high values of ϕ_B would result in very high recirculating flowrates and the oversizing of pumping equipment.

2.2. Experimental tests

Tests were conducted with a live saturated steam flowrate of $\dot{m}_S = 100 \text{ kg/h}$ at 11 bar. Firstly, make-up water was introduced into the cycle

with a conductivity k_A . Then the cycle was started up, and once steady conditions were reached, electrical conductivity was measured by sampling the most relevant streams for HCT operation, i.e., boiler feedwater (k_F), live steam (k_S), boiler blowdown (k_B), and cooling reflux (k_R). Note that, as no turbine bleeding was performed during the tests ($\dot{m}_D = 0$), the conductivity of the make-up water to the cycle k_A is the same as the condensate from the steam absorber k_C and boiler feedwater k_F . Tests were performed with several combinations of conductivity values of the boiler feedwater (k_F) from 0.31 to 32,530 $\mu\text{S/cm}$ and blowdown volumetric flowrates (V_B) from 1 to 10 L/h, as shown in

Table 1
Conditions for the experimental tests performed.

$k_F [\mu S/cm]$	$\dot{V}_B [L/h]$
0.31	1
2.23	3
20.4	5
95.06	7
500	10
2,002	
5,640	
19,840	
32,530	

Table 1. Ambient temperatures were stable during the realization of the tests (15–19 °C). In addition, the power of the dry cooling system was adaptively controlled so that the temperature drop inside the cycle after cooling did not depend on the ambient temperature.

In order to make electrical conductivity data comparable, the stream samples were all cooled to 25 °C before measuring their conductivity. Then, COC were determined using Eq. (2). Operating conditions at the pilot plant have been measured with appropriate instrumentation at each cycle point. Temperatures have been generally measured with WIKA TC10-0 cooper-constantan T-type thermocouples (accuracy ± 0.2 °C), but Endress + Haussner TR-61 platinum resistances PT100 RTD temperature sensors (accuracy ± 0.1 °C) were used for obtaining more precise values at the absorber inlet and outlet flows. Pressure was measured with Aplisens PCE-28 (accuracy ± 0.5%) pressure sensors, whereas flowrates were measured with Khrono OPTISWIRL-5080 flowmeters (accuracy ± 0.5%). SIMATIC S7 control system from SIEMENS [28] allows to visualize, record and control all variables with a maximum uncertainty of 0.004%. Electrical conductivity values were also obtained with portable equipment (HANNA HI 98188–02 conductivity meter, accuracy ± 2% [44]), using purge points for sampling steam and liquid flows [45]. Finally, network analyzers were also available for measuring overall electric consumption of the power plant and of each component. The sampling of values was performed 10 h per

day, with data acquisition every 20 min, while steam and blowdown flows were continuously measured.

Pressures and temperatures of the condensate at the absorber outlet have been measured as well. The results have allowed to compare the real condensing temperatures (T_{Cond}) with the condensing temperatures of pure water (T_{Cond-H_2O}), quantifying the temperature rise ΔT_{Cond} produced by the hygroscopic effect due to the different concentrations of the steam and the cooling reflux:

$$\Delta T_{Cond} = T_{Cond} - T_{Cond-H_2O} \quad (4)$$

2.3. Mass and species model

Mass and concentration balances were solved throughout the cycle using the Engineering Equation Solver software (EES, version V10.833-3D) [46], focusing on the two most relevant components of the cycle: the absorber (core component of HCT for condensation) and the boiler (importance of COC control). The specific mass flows, mass flow ratios and conductivities are shown in Fig. 4.

The equations that define the model for the boiler are the following:

■ Mass balance

$$\dot{m}_F = \dot{m}_S + \dot{m}_B \text{ with } \phi_B = \frac{\dot{m}_B}{\dot{m}_F} \quad (5)$$

■ Concentration balance

$$\dot{m}_F k_F = \dot{m}_S k_S + \dot{m}_B k_B \rightarrow k_F = (1 - \phi_B) k_S + \phi_B k_B \quad (6)$$

The following relationships between the boiler feedwater, boiler blowdown and live steam conductivities as a function of the blowdown flow ratio were obtained:

$$k_B = \frac{k_F + (\phi_B - 1)k_S}{\phi_B} \text{ and } k_S = \frac{k_F - \phi_B k_B}{1 - \phi_B} \quad (7)$$

The absorber model, which required an additional balance in the node where the boiler blowdown is mixed with the recirculation of the

Fig. 4. Mass and species balances in the HCT pilot plant.

condensate flow, is based on the following equations:

■ Absorber mass balance

$$\dot{m}_S + \dot{m}_R = \dot{m}_C \rightarrow (1 - \phi_B)\dot{m}_F + \phi_B\dot{m}_F + \phi_R\dot{m}_C = \dot{m}_C \rightarrow \dot{m}_F = (1 - \phi_R)\dot{m}_C \quad (8)$$

■ Node mass balance

$$\dot{m}_R = \dot{m}_B + \phi_R\dot{m}_C = \phi_B\dot{m}_F + \phi_R\dot{m}_C = \left(\frac{\phi_B + \phi_R - \phi_B\phi_R}{1 - \phi_R} \right) \dot{m}_F \quad (9)$$

■ Absorber concentration balance

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{m}_S k_S + \dot{m}_R k_R &= \dot{m}_C k_C \rightarrow (1 - \phi_B)k_S + \left(\frac{\phi_B + \phi_R - \phi_B\phi_R}{1 - \phi_R} \right) k_R \\ &= \frac{1}{1 - \phi_P} k_F \text{ with } k_C = k_F \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Validation of the model

Fig. 5 shows the blowdown (k_B) and live steam (k_S) conductivity values predicted by the mass and species model as a function of the blowdown ratio ϕ_B , alongside the experimental results obtained from the pilot plant. Considering the wide range of feedwater conductivity (k_F) values tested, the results for each variable have been subdivided into two plots for the sake of clarity, with the bottom one focusing on the lowest conductivity values. It may be observed that the model is able to capture the tendency of the experimental results. It must be noted that by measuring the feedwater conductivity and the blowdown ratio, it is possible to estimate the conductivities of the rest of the cycle streams by

using the mass and species model, reducing thus the instrumentation required in the power plant.

3.2. Boiler operation

Once the model was validated with the experimental results, estimates were made for the range of feedwater conductivities k_F from 0.01 to 50,000 $\mu\text{S/cm}$. Figs. 6 and 7 show the results for different feedwater conductivity isolines, so the corresponding values for blowdown and live steam conductivities may be obtained if the blowdown ratio is known. The increase in the blowdown ratio contributes to decreasing the conductivity of the streams coming out of the boiler, both the blowdown and the live steam. This decrease is sharper in the lower range of ϕ_B and for higher k_F values, with the evolution of both k_S and k_B becoming more stable at the higher range of ϕ_B and with lower k_F . It may be observed how, for low blowdown stream values, the conductivity of the live steam approaches that of the incoming boiler feedwater, whereas the blowdown conductivity increases towards infinity in the limit case $\phi_B = 0$. This effect may be explained by the fact that the blowdown concentration and boiler COC increase with the decrease in the boiler purges, with smaller flowrates that contain more concentrated impurities. As a consequence, it is impossible to clean the live steam from impurities, reaching $k_S = k_F$ in the limit case $\phi_B = 0$. On the other hand, with the increase in boiler blowdown, the live steam becomes less concentrated in impurities, as well as the blowdown itself, due to the reduction in the boiler COC. An absurd is reached in the models for the limit case of $\phi_B = 100\%$. At this limit, all the boiler feedwater is purged from the boiler, so $k_P = k_F$. There is no steam production, so the value of k_S remains undetermined.

The effect of the boiler outlet stream conductivities variation may be appreciated in Fig. 8, which shows the evolution of the boiler Cycles Of Concentration as a function of the boiler blowdown ratio. The data

Fig. 5. Boiler blowdown and live steam conductivity values as a function of blowdown ratio and feedwater conductivity (model – solid lines, experimental results – squares).

Fig. 6. Boiler blowdown conductivity values as a function of blowdown ratio and feedwater conductivity.

collected from the experiments have been averaged, allowing to show the 95% confidence interval in which the COC may be expected if ϕ_B is controlled. The effect of the actual value of the feedwater conductivity is not reflected strongly in the COC, so this may hint to a possible control of COC to satisfy the boiler manufacturer requirements by relying just in the flowrate of boiler purges. As with the electrical conductivities shown in Figs. 6 and 7, the decrease of the COC is quite sharp for the lowest ϕ_B . Once $\phi_B = 5\%$ is reached, COC becomes stabilized in the range below 20. It may be assumed that $\phi_B > 10\%$ is not going to reduce COC to substantially lower values, if the beneficial effect of reduction is compared with the thermal energy losses related to purging the boiler.

In addition to the possible thermal energy losses with the increase of boiler blowdowns, an increase in the mass flowrate diverted from the boiler will increase the required power consumption by the feedwater pump, as shown in Fig. 9. The evolution of the specific power consumption of the feedwater pump as a function of the blowdown ratio shows an increase of approximately 0.42 kJ/kg per each additional 1% of boiler purges. Considering that state-of-the-art power plants use relatively high mass flowrates, this increase should be considered due to their impact in the plant net power production [7]. Hence, boiler blowdowns may be balanced between keeping the required boiler COC, while at the same time maintaining a reasonable increase of thermal

energy losses from the boiler and pumping power increase.

3.3. Turbine and absorber operation

Apart from providing insight into the working conditions at the cycle boiler, the results from the experiments and the subsequent modeling have been able to understand the rest of key cycle equipment. The cycle operation must be properly controlled to ensure the absorption process and equipment protection. In this sense, to prevent turbine damage, live steam conductivity values (and thus impurities in water droplets drawn by the steam) should lie below 0.2 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ [28,29]. In addition, it was experimentally verified that the conductivity of the cooling reflux k_R should be above 1.1 times the conductivity of the live steam k_S for absorption to occur. Otherwise, as observed in the pilot plant tests, the difference in the content of hygroscopic compounds in the live steam and cooling reflux is too low to produce condensation by absorption. Following these constraints, Fig. 10 shows different boiler feedwater conductivities and blowdown ratio values combinations. Different lines depict the boundaries between operation ranges depending on the previously commented technical constraints. The red zone, below the value of $k_R/k_S = 1.1$, defines the operating range in which the absorption process is not feasible. Above the corresponding value of k_F , where the

Fig. 7. Live steam conductivity values as a function of blowdown ratio and feedwater conductivity.

technology is able to operate properly, two different zones are delimited by the line of boiler feedwater conductivity k_f that corresponds to a live steam conductivity of $k_s = 0.2 \mu\text{S/cm}$. Below this line, the area depicted in green represents the operational range where the cycle can work without the need of a droplet separator to protect the turbine [47]. The blue zone outlined above, however, requires the use of the separator to prevent water droplets of high conductivity to be drawn into the turbine. The three zones meet at a single point, as shown in the zoom performed in Fig. 10, which corresponds to $\phi_B = 0.04\%$. Only above this minimum blowdown ratio is it possible to operate the HCT cycle without requiring a droplet separator.

After identifying the limits for operating the technology, Fig. 11 shows the relationship between live steam, cooling reflux and boiler feedwater conductivities as a function of the blowdown ratio. As previously stated, and according to the results, with the appropriate blowdown ratios, HCT cycles can work with high feedwater electrical conductivities, as the blowdown is performed continuously. The blue line depicts the evolution of the cooling reflux conductivity, showing its independence from the boiler blowdown ratio. The green lines depict the change in the live steam conductivity as a function of ϕ_B . The red region represents the zone where condensation by absorption is impossible, due to the proximity of k_R and k_s , delimited by the line of

$\phi_B = 0.04\%$. It may be appreciated that with blowdown ratio values above 10%, the further decrease in k_s becomes very low. This fact suggests the recommendation of not using higher boiler blowdown ratios, as they will result in a substantial increase of boiler fuel consumption and pumping power with no associated significant improvement of the live steam quality.

3.4. Hygroscopic effects in the absorber

Finally, the effect of the hygroscopic compound concentration in the cooling reflux has been analyzed with the pressure and temperature measurements from the pilot plant. Fig. 12 shows the evolution of the condensing pressure P_{Cond} as a function of the condensing temperature T_{Cond} and the cooling reflux electrical conductivity k_R . The hygroscopic effect due to the difference in the electrical conductivities of the exhaust steam from the turbine and the cooling reflux when they mix in the absorber causes a reduction in the condensing pressure for a given temperature, which becomes more apparent as the difference between both conductivities rises. The decrease in the condensing pressure may be linked to a higher enthalpy jump at the turbine and, thus, a higher power output and cycle efficiency.

Parallely, for a given condensing pressure P_c , the hygroscopic effect

Fig. 8. Boiler Cycles Of Concentration as a function of boiler blowdown ratio (squares – experimental data).

Fig. 9. Pump power consumption vs boiler blowdown volume flowrate.

caused by the difference in the electrical conductivities (i.e., the concentration of impurities) of steam and cooling reflux generates a temperature increase ΔT_{Cond} with respect to the condensing temperature of pure water. Fig. 13 shows the experimentally measured temperature increase as a function of P_{Cond} and k_R , where it may be appreciated that increases up to 0.7 °C in the condensate temperature may be achieved. The effect of the electrical conductivity of the cooling reflux is more apparent than that of the condensing pressure. For the sake of clarity, the experimental values have been averaged, showing a 95% confidence interval of the temperature increase with respect to k_R for the measured values. It may be appreciated that the temperature increase is almost constant (0.3 °C) up to $k_R = 500 \mu S/cm$, increasing exponentially for higher conductivity values. This leads to potentially higher temperatures in the stream to be cooled if k_R is further increased, making easier to release heat into the environment.

4. Conclusion

In this work, the influence of the concentration of hygroscopic salts in the Hygroscopic Cycle Technology (HCT) has been studied, providing insight into the proper operation ranges of the cycle and identifying the key operational parameters. An experimental study of the influence of make-up water quality, with the concentration of impurities measured by water electrical conductivity, and cycle mass flow ratio values has

Fig. 10. Control of live steam and cooling reflux conductivity as a function of feedwater conductivity and blowdown ratio (squares – experimental results).

been performed in a pilot plant. The results, used to validate a mass and species conservation model of the cycle, have allowed to obtain the conductivity values of the different cycle streams with just the input of the feedwater conductivity and the blowdown ratio in the boiler. This has allowed to generate charts for the proper operation of the technology, as well as support the reduction in the amount of instrumentation required control the cycle performance.

The increase of the boiler blowdown ratio ϕ_B contributed to decrease the conductivity of the live steam and the blowdown streams, with a sharper decrease for lower ϕ_B values and a more stable evolution of conductivities once ϕ_B reached values around 5%. The reduction in the Cycles Of Concentration (COC) of the boiler exhibited a similar evolution, stabilizing around a value of 20. The feedwater conductivity value and the blowdown ratio affected the conductivities of both live steam and blowdown streams; nevertheless, COC were mainly dependent from the blowdown ratio. Although the HCT has an enthalpic recuperator that recovers a high percentage of the thermal energy from the boiler blowdown, it was found that blowdown ratio values above 10% did not reduce COC to substantially lower values in comparison with the thermal energy losses associated with boiler blowdown. In addition, an increase in the feedwater pump work of 0.42 kJ/kg per each additional 1% of boiler purges was found. Hence, although the HCT cycle can work with high conductivities thanks to the continuous boiler blowdown, a compromise between keeping the required boiler COC and a reasonable

Fig. 11. Relationship between live steam, cooling reflux and boiler feedwater conductivity as a function of blowdown ratio.

Fig. 12. Absorber condensing pressure as function of cooling reflux conductivity for different condensing temperatures.

Fig. 13. Temperature increase as function of cooling reflux conductivity for different condensing pressures.

increase of thermal energy losses from the boiler and pumping power must be found.

The results have also provided insight into the necessary conditions to achieve condensation in the cycle absorber and protecting the cycle equipment from problems derived from water impurities. It was found that the conductivity of the cooling reflux had to be 1.1 times the conductivity of the turbine steam for condensation by absorption to occur. In addition, the values of the blowdown ratio required as a function of the boiler feedwater conductivity for the turbine to work without the need of a droplet separator are provided, with a minimum $\phi_B = 0.04\%$. However, it was found that blowdown ratios above 10% would result in a substantial increase of boiler fuel consumption and pumping power with no associated significant improvement of the live steam quality.

Finally, the study of the hygroscopic effects in the absorber has allowed to identify the decrease of the condensing pressure for a given condensing temperature, which is associated to a higher enthalpy jump at the steam turbine and may be linked to a higher cycle power output. In parallel, for a given condensing pressure, the condensing temperature increases thanks to the hygroscopic effects, resulting in increases up to 0.7 °C in the condensate temperature at pilot plant scale, leading to potentially higher temperatures in the cooling stream of industrial power cycles which may make easier to reject heat from the cycle.

The findings and model presented in this study provide valuable information towards the real operation of the HCT cycle at an industrial scale. The developed performance charts may be used to keep the cycle within optimal conditions, thanks to the identification of the most relevant operational parameters, blowdown ratio, COC and feedwater electrical conductivity, and their optimal values. As a consequence, the amount of monitoring instrumentation in the cycle may be reduced. Experiments in pilot plants, such as the ones performed in this study, allow to understand the behavior of the hygroscopic cycle and verify the proper operation ranges of the technology, considering effects that are normally disregarded in theoretical models, i.e., precipitation of salts or corrosion of materials. Nevertheless, similar tests at industrial scale would be interesting in future studies, as the boiler size limits the extend of the tests that may be performed. Future research could include the experimental evaluation of salt precipitation and its effect on the potential redistribution of flows and the useful life of the equipment, as well as the comparison between the behaviors of different hygroscopic compounds and their impact on the cycle. Experimental characterization of aqueous mixtures of these compounds at the temperatures and pressures required in the industry will be useful for the successful implementation of this technology.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The authors do not have permission to share further data.

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